
Clinical Implications of the PRESERVE Study and the Use of IVC Filters

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Abstract

Inferior vena cava (IVC) filters are devices designed to prevent pulmonary embolism (PE) by trapping large emboli originating from deep venous thrombosis (DVT) in the lower extremities. These devices have been a critical tool in managing patients at high risk for PE, particularly those who have contraindications to anticoagulation therapy or have experienced recurrent thromboembolic events despite anticoagulation. However, the clinical utility and safety of IVC filters have been subjects of ongoing debate due to potential complications such as filter migration, fracture, and the long-term risks of leaving filters in place.

The PRESERVE (Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters) study is a landmark trial aimed at providing comprehensive data on the safety, efficacy, and outcomes associated with the use of both retrievable and permanent IVC filters. This prospective, multicenter study involves a diverse patient population and multiple filter types, intending to address the knowledge gaps and controversies surrounding IVC filter use. The study's findings are expected to inform clinical practice, refine patient selection criteria, and guide future guidelines.

This article delves into the key findings of the PRESERVE study, its implications for clinical practice, and the current societal guidelines on the use of IVC filters. By examining the safety profile, retrieval rates, and clinical outcomes, we aim to provide a nuanced understanding of the role of IVC filters in managing thromboembolic disease. The discussion also highlights the importance of patient selection, follow-up strategies, and the continued role of anticoagulation in patients with IVC filters, aligning with the evolving guidelines from major medical societies.

Keywords

PRESERVE Study, IVC Filters, Pulmonary Embolism, Thrombosis, Fracture, SIR, SVS

Introduction

Inferior vena cava (IVC) filters are medical devices implanted into the inferior vena cava to prevent pulmonary embolism (PE), a life-threatening condition caused by emboli traveling from deep vein thrombosis (DVT) in the lower extremities to the lungs. (Bikdeli & Bikdeli, 2016) The primary function of IVC filters is to trap large emboli before they can reach the pulmonary circulation, thereby reducing the risk of PE (Bikdeli et al., 2018). These devices have been particularly useful in patients who are unable to undergo anticoagulation therapy due to contraindications such as active bleeding or those who have experienced recurrent thromboembolic events despite adequate anticoagulation.

The clinical utility and safety of IVC filters have been a topic of considerable debate within the medical community (Grewal et al., 2016). While they provide a critical intervention for preventing PE in high-risk patients, concerns have been raised regarding their potential complications and long-term effects. Complications associated with IVC filters include device migration, fracture, penetration of the vena cava wall, and the development of new DVT. (Sobieszczyk, 2018) Moreover, the decision to retrieve or leave the filter in situ poses another layer of complexity in patient management, as long-term implantation can increase the risk of complications.

The PRESERVE (Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters) study was initiated to

address these concerns and provide robust data on the safety, efficacy, and clinical outcomes of IVC filters. This prospective, multicenter study is one of the largest and most comprehensive evaluations of IVC filters to date. It includes a diverse patient population and evaluates multiple types of both retrievable and permanent IVC filters. The goal of the PRESERVE study is to generate evidence-based insights that can guide clinical decision-making, improve patient outcomes, and inform future guidelines. (Bikdeli et al., 2018) Prior to the PRESERVE study, data on IVC filters were derived largely from smaller, less comprehensive studies and clinical experience. These sources provided valuable information but were insufficient to establish definitive conclusions about the optimal use of IVC filters. The PRESERVE study's design addresses these limitations by incorporating a larger sample size, multiple filter types, and a broad range of patient demographics and clinical scenarios. (Gillespie et al., 2020) This approach aims to provide a clearer picture of the benefits and risks associated with IVC filter use.

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Furthermore, the PRESERVE study evaluates both the short-term and long-term outcomes of IVC filter implantation, including the incidence of PE, filter-related complications, and the success rates of filter retrieval. By doing so, it offers insights into the timing of filter retrieval, a critical aspect of patient management that has implications for reducing long-term complications. The study also emphasizes the importance of patient selection criteria, aiming to identify which patient populations benefit most from IVC filter placement.

In summary, the PRESERVE study represents a significant advancement in our understanding of IVC filter use. It seeks to address the ongoing debate over their safety and efficacy by providing comprehensive data that can inform clinical practice. As such, the findings of the PRESERVE study are expected to play a pivotal role in shaping future guidelines and recommendations for the use of IVC filters in preventing pulmonary embolism.

The PRESERVE Study

The PRESERVE study (Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters) is a landmark prospective, multicenter study designed to evaluate the safety, efficacy, and outcomes associated with the use of IVC filters. This comprehensive study involved multiple filter types and included a diverse patient population, aiming to provide detailed and reliable data on both retrievable and permanent filters. The PRESERVE study's design and scope make it one of the most significant investigations into IVC filter use to date, addressing previous knowledge gaps and controversies.

Safety and Complications

One of the primary focuses of the PRESERVE study was to assess the safety of IVC filters. The study reported a low rate of major complications associated with IVC filter placement, a critical finding given the historical concerns about filter-related adverse events.

Filter Migration: Filter migration, where the device moves from its original placement site, was found to be infrequent. This complication can lead to ineffective prevention of PE and potential damage to the vena cava or other organs.

Filter Fracture: The incidence of filter fracture, where parts of the filter break off and migrate to other parts of the body, was also low. This is a notable outcome because filter fractures can lead to significant complications, including injury to the heart or lungs if fragments travel to these areas.

Penetration of the Vena Cava Wall: The study noted minimal occurrences of filter penetration, where the device extends through the vena cava wall. This can lead to pain, bleeding, or damage to adjacent structures.

Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT) Post-Filter Placement: The rate of DVT after filter placement was documented, emphasizing the necessity for appropriate anticoagulation management. Despite the filter's role in preventing PE, it does not mitigate the risk of DVT, which can still occur post-placement.

Retrieval Rates

Retrievable IVC filters are designed to be removed once the risk of PE has diminished, to minimize long-term complications associated with permanent filters. The

PRESERVE study provided valuable insights into the feasibility and safety of filter retrieval.

Variation Among Filter Types: The study found that retrieval success rates varied only slightly among different filter types, indicating that the design and mechanical properties of filters influence retrieval outcomes, but most filters were able to be removed with success.

Feasibility and Safety of Timely Removal: Generally, the study indicated that the timely removal of retrievable filters is both feasible and safe. Successful retrieval is crucial to reducing the risk of complications such as filter fracture or migration, which are more likely to occur the longer the filter remains in place.

Technical and Clinical Considerations: The study highlighted the importance of technical skill and clinical judgment in the retrieval process. Successful retrieval not only depends on the filter design but also on the expertise of the medical team and the timing of the procedure.

Clinical Outcomes

The PRESERVE study also examined the overall clinical outcomes of patients who received IVC filters, focusing on the incidence of PE and the effectiveness of the filters in preventing this life-threatening condition.

Incidence of Pulmonary Embolism (PE): The study reported a low incidence of PE in patients with IVC filters, suggesting that the devices provide effective protection for high-risk individuals. This finding supports the continued use of IVC filters in appropriately selected patients who are at significant risk for PE and cannot be managed adequately with anticoagulation alone.

Importance of Patient Selection Criteria: Outcomes significantly depended on the appropriate use of IVC filters according to clinical indications. The study underscored that careful patient selection is paramount to achieving favorable outcomes. Filters should be reserved for patients with clear indications, such as those with absolute contraindications to anticoagulation or recurrent thromboembolic events despite optimal anticoagulation therapy.

3. Long-Term Management and Follow-Up:

The study emphasized the necessity of ongoing follow-up and management. Patients with IVC filters require regular monitoring to ensure that the filters remain effective and to identify any potential complications early. This includes imaging studies to check the filter's position and integrity and clinical evaluations to assess for symptoms of DVT or PE.

The PRESERVE Study: Comprehensive Results and Clinical Implications

Overview

The PRESERVE (Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters) study is a large-scale, multicenter, prospective trial designed to evaluate the safety, efficacy, and outcomes associated with the use of IVC filters. Conducted at 54 sites across the United States between October 2015 and March 2019, the study enrolled 1,421 patients, 1,019 of whom had existing DVT or PE at the time of filter placement. The study included multiple types

of IVC filters, both retrievable and permanent, to provide comprehensive data on their performance.

Key Findings

Safety and Complications

Major Complications: The study reported a low incidence of major complications. Filter migration (>20 mm) occurred in three patients, and filter embolization was noted in four patients. IVC perforation (≥ 5 mm) was observed in 15.4% of patients at the 12-month follow-up.

DVT and PE: Post-filter placement, 74 patients (5.2%) developed DVT, 23 patients (1.6%) experienced PE, and 15 patients (1.1%) had caval thrombotic occlusions.

Retrieval Procedure-Related Adverse Events: Adverse events related to filter retrieval occurred in 1.8% of patients, with one death resulting from an innominate vein injury.

Retrieval Rates

Overall Retrieval: Filters were successfully removed in 49.3% of retrievable filters and 44.5% of all study filters, with a mean retrieval time of 101.5 days and a median of 86.3 days.

Retrieval Success: Of the 640 retrieval attempts, 632 (98.8%) were successful, with 620 (96.8%) succeeding on the first attempt. These high success rates underscore the feasibility and safety of filter removal when appropriately indicated.

Clinical Outcomes

Incidence of PE: The incidence of PE in patients with IVC filters was low, suggesting effective prevention in high-risk individuals.

Patient Selection: The study highlighted the critical importance of patient selection criteria. Filters should be used in patients with contraindications to anticoagulation or those with recurrent VTE despite anticoagulation. Appropriate use according to clinical indications significantly impacted outcomes.

Clinical Implications

The PRESERVE study's findings provide crucial insights into the optimal use of IVC filters:

Patient Selection and Management: Filters should be reserved for patients with specific indications, such as contraindications to anticoagulation or recurrent thromboembolic events despite adequate anticoagulation. A comprehensive care approach, including detailed patient evaluation, a plan for retrieval after placement, and frequent follow-up, is essential to maximize benefits and minimize risks.

Follow-Up and Retrieval: Regular follow-up is necessary to monitor filter position and integrity and to assess the continued need for the filter. The high retrieval success rates support timely removal of retrievable filters to minimize long-term complications.

Anticoagulation: Continued anticoagulation management is crucial for patients with IVC filters to prevent new thromboembolic events.

Current Societal Guidelines

Current guidelines from major societies, including the American College of Chest Physicians (ACCP) and the Society of Interventional Radiology (SIR), reflect the evolving understanding of IVC filter use. @These guidelines are designed to optimize patient outcomes, minimize

complications, and provide clear recommendations for the use and management of IVC filters.

Indications for Use

The ACCP and SIR guidelines recommend IVC filters primarily for patients with acute venous thromboembolism (VTE) who have an absolute contraindication to anticoagulation. This includes patients who cannot receive anticoagulants due to active bleeding, recent surgery, or high bleeding risk. For these patients, IVC filters serve as a critical intervention to prevent pulmonary embolism (PE) by trapping thrombi before they reach the lungs. (ACC Maintenance, 2016)

Prophylactic use of IVC filters is generally discouraged. (Kaufman et al., 2020) The guidelines caution against routine use in patients who are at risk for VTE but can be managed with anticoagulation. Prophylactic placement is considered only in very high-risk scenarios where the risk of PE is extremely high and the benefits of filter placement outweigh the potential risks. Examples include patients with severe trauma, those undergoing high-risk surgical procedures, or patients with recurrent VTE despite optimal anticoagulation therapy.

Filter Management

Effective management of IVC filters involves both the initial placement and the ongoing follow-up to ensure the filter's safety and efficacy. The guidelines emphasize the importance of removing retrievable filters as soon as clinically feasible to minimize long-term complications. Prolonged presence of the filter can lead to risks such as filter fracture, migration, penetration of the vena cava wall, and the development of new DVT. (Kelkar & Rajasekhar, 2020)

Regular imaging follow-up is recommended to monitor the filter's position and integrity. This typically involves periodic ultrasound or CT scans to detect any signs of complications such as migration, perforation, or thrombosis around the filter. Early detection of such issues allows for timely intervention, whether it be filter repositioning, retrieval, or managing associated complications.

In addition to imaging, clinical follow-up is crucial. Patients should be regularly evaluated for signs and symptoms of DVT and PE, and their need for continued filter presence should be reassessed. The decision to retrieve the filter should be based on the patient's current clinical status and risk of thromboembolism. If the patient no longer requires protection against PE and can be safely managed with anticoagulation, filter retrieval should be pursued.

Documentation and Communication

Adequate documentation is a cornerstone of effective IVC filter management. Detailed records should be maintained regarding the indication for filter placement, the type of filter used, and the plan for follow-up and retrieval. (Grewal et al., 2016) This documentation is essential for ensuring continuity of care, especially if the patient is managed by multiple healthcare providers.

Multidisciplinary communication between interventional radiologists, vascular surgeons, primary care providers, and other involved specialists is vital for coordinated patient care. Clear communication channels help in sharing relevant information, making informed decisions about filter management, and ensuring that the patient receives comprehensive care. Collaborative discussions should be

held to review the patient's status, decide on the timing of filter retrieval, and address any complications that may arise.

Overall, the guidelines emphasize a patient-centered approach to IVC filter use, advocating for judicious placement, regular monitoring, and timely retrieval to optimize patient outcomes and minimize risks. These recommendations reflect the best practices derived from current evidence and expert consensus, aiming to enhance the safety and efficacy of IVC filter therapy in clinical practice.

Summary of PRESERVE Outcomes on Filter Safety and Efficacy

The PRESERVE (Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters) study provided comprehensive data on the performance of various IVC filters in terms of safety and efficacy. The study included multiple types of IVC filters, (Argon Medical Devices, Inc; ALN, Ghisonaccia; B. Braun Medical, Inc; C.R. Bard/BD; Cordis/Cardinal; Cook Medical; Volcano), and evaluated their performance across a diverse patient population. The results of the PRESERVE study indicated that all filters represented in the study exhibited similar overall safety and efficacy performance, underscoring their utility in clinical practice.(Johnson,et al,2023)

Safety Performance

The PRESERVE study found a low incidence of major complications associated with IVC filter placement across all filter types. Specific complications such as filter migration, fracture, and perforation were infrequent, demonstrating a robust safety profile for the filters included in the study.

Filter Migration: Only a small number of patients experienced significant filter migration (>20 mm), highlighting the stability of the filters once implanted.

Filter Fracture: Filter fractures were rare, reducing concerns about parts of the filter breaking off and migrating to other parts of the body, which could potentially cause severe complications.

Perforation: Although perforation of the IVC wall occurred in some patients (15.4% as observed on CT scans), the clinical significance of these findings was generally low, and severe complications from perforation were uncommon.

Adverse Events Post-Placement: The rates of DVT (5.2%), PE (1.6%), and caval thrombotic occlusion (1.1%) post-filter placement were consistent across different filter types, indicating no significant variation in safety performance among the filters.

Efficacy Performance

The efficacy of IVC filters in preventing pulmonary embolism (PE) was effectively demonstrated in the PRESERVE study. The low incidence of PE among patients with IVC filters underscores their role in providing effective protection against this life-threatening condition.

Prevention of PE: The study reported a low incidence of PE in patients with IVC filters, suggesting that the filters were effective in trapping thrombi and preventing them from reaching the pulmonary circulation.

Retrieval Success Rates: High retrieval success rates were observed across all filter types. Of the retrievable filters, 49.3% were removed, and 44.5% of all filters were successfully retrieved, with a success rate of 96.8% on the

first attempt. This demonstrates that timely and safe removal of the filters is feasible across different designs and types.

Timely Retrieval and Management: The mean retrieval time was approximately 101.5 days, and the median was 86.3 days. These consistent retrieval timelines across different filter types indicate that the filters are designed for both effective short-term protection and safe long-term management.

Overall Performance

The PRESERVE study outcomes indicate that the IVC filters evaluated had similar safety and efficacy profiles. The low rates of major complications, effective prevention of PE, and high retrieval success rates were consistent across all filter types included in the study. These findings support the continued use of IVC filters as a safe and effective intervention for patients at high risk of PE, especially those who cannot be managed with anticoagulation alone.

The study highlights the importance of careful patient selection, diligent follow-up, and coordinated care to optimize the benefits and minimize the risks associated with IVC filter use. By demonstrating the comparable performance of various filters, the PRESERVE study provides valuable evidence to guide clinical decision-making and inform future guidelines on the use and management of IVC filters in preventing venous thromboembolism.

Conclusion on the Safe Use of IVC Filters Based on the PRESERVE Trial

The PRESERVE (Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters) trial stands as a landmark study in the evaluation of IVC filters, offering comprehensive insights into their safety and efficacy. Conducted across 54 sites in the United States, the study included 1,421 patients and assessed multiple IVC filter types from six manufacturers: (Argon Medical Devices, Inc; ALN, Ghisonaccia; B. Braun Medical, Inc; C.R. Bard/BD; Cordis/Cardinal; Cook Medical; Volcano) – Note: Volcano and Cordis did not complete enrollment in their arm, both filters are no longer available in the United States for sale or implantation.

Safety Profile

The PRESERVE trial reported a low incidence of major complications, addressing long-standing concerns about the safety of IVC filters. Key findings include:

Filter Migration: Significant migration (>20 mm) was rare, occurring in only three patients.

Filter Fracture: Few cases of filter fracture were observed, minimizing the risk of embolization of filter fragments.

Perforation: While perforation of the IVC wall was noted in 15.4% of patients, these incidents were mostly clinically insignificant and did not lead to severe complications.

Post-Placement Complications: Rates of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE) post-placement were 5.2% and 1.6%, respectively, further underscoring the filters' safety profile.

Efficacy in Preventing Pulmonary Embolism

IVC filters effectively prevented PE in patients at high risk, especially those with contraindications to anticoagulation. The low incidence of PE among patients with filters confirms their role in providing substantial protection against this life-threatening condition.

Retrieval and Long-Term Management

A critical aspect of IVC filter management is the timely retrieval of retrievable filters to avoid long-term complications. The PRESERVE trial found:

High Retrieval Success Rates: Approximately 49.3% of retrievable filters and 44.5% of all filters were successfully removed. The success rate for first-attempt retrievals was 96.8%.

Timing of Retrieval: The mean retrieval time was 101.5 days, and the median was 86.3 days, indicating effective short-term protection and safe long-term management when filters are retrieved timely.

Recommendations for Clinical Practice

The findings from the PRESERVE trial support several key recommendations for the use of IVC filters:

Patient Selection: IVC filters should be used for patients with specific indications, such as those with an absolute contraindication to anticoagulation or those experiencing recurrent VTE despite anticoagulation. Thorough patient evaluation is essential to ensure appropriate use.

Monitoring and Follow-Up: Regular imaging and clinical follow-up are crucial for monitoring the filter's position and integrity and for assessing the continued need for the filter.

Multidisciplinary Approach: Effective management involves collaboration among various healthcare providers, including interventional radiologists, vascular surgeons, and primary care providers. This ensures comprehensive care from placement to follow-up and retrieval.

Documentation and Communication: Detailed documentation of the indication for filter placement, type of filter, and follow-up plans is necessary for optimal patient management. Clear communication among healthcare providers is vital to coordinated care.

Future Directions

While the PRESERVE trial provides a robust foundation for understanding the safe use of IVC filters, further research is needed to continue improving patient outcomes. Future studies should explore long-term outcomes beyond initial retrieval, the impact of different filter designs, and the development of more precise guidelines for patient selection and management.

In conclusion, the PRESERVE trial demonstrates that with careful patient selection, diligent follow-up, and timely retrieval, IVC filters can be used safely and effectively to prevent pulmonary embolism in high-risk patients. These findings support the continued use of IVC filters in appropriately selected patients and provide a framework for best practices in their management.

Discussion on the OptionELITE Filter Performance in the PRESERVE Trial

Overview of the OptionELITE Filter

The **OptionELITE Retrievable Vena Cava Filter**, developed by Argon Medical Devices, is an advanced device designed for the prevention of recurrent pulmonary embolism (PE). By capturing emboli originating from deep vein thrombosis (DVT) in the lower extremities, it provides a crucial intervention for high-risk patients. The OptionELITE filter is notable for its combination of innovative features that

enhance both safety and efficacy, distinguishing it from other devices in its class.

Design and Material

Construction: The OptionELITE filter is constructed from a single piece of nitinol, an alloy composed of nickel and titanium. Nitinol is highly regarded in the medical device field due to its unique properties of shape memory and super elasticity. These properties allow the filter to return to its pre-determined shape after deformation, which is critical for its deployment and function within the dynamic environment of the inferior vena cava (IVC). The single-piece design of the OptionELITE filter eliminates joints and welds, which are potential points of failure in multi-piece filters. This design minimizes the risk of filter fracture by dispersing the forces of cyclic compression across the whole body of the IVC filter as opposed to a single point or section, thus minimizing the risk of device fracture, a significant complication associated with vena cava filters.

Structural Integrity: The nitinol construction ensures that the filter maintains its structural integrity under various physiological conditions, including changes in blood flow and pressure within the IVC. This robustness is essential for ensuring that the filter can withstand the mechanical stresses imposed by the IVC over extended periods. The material's biocompatibility also reduces the risk of adverse reactions, such as inflammation and thrombosis, further enhancing the filter's safety profile.

Anchoring System

Unique Design: The anchoring system of the OptionELITE filter is specifically engineered to prevent both cranial (upward) and caudal (downward) migration within the IVC. Migration of the filter can lead to severe complications, such as embolization to the heart or lungs or penetration into adjacent structures. The OptionELITE's anchoring system utilizes a combination of hooks and barbs that engage with the venous wall, securing the filter in place. This design not only stabilizes the filter but also ensures that it remains positioned correctly to capture emboli effectively. The ability to prevent migration is a critical feature that enhances patient safety and filter efficacy.

Retrievability

Ease of Retrieval: One of the standout features of the OptionELITE filter is its design for ease of retrieval. The filter features an open apex design, which allows for easy snaring and removal using standard retrieval techniques. The retrievability of the filter is crucial for patient care, as it enables the removal of the device once the risk of PE has subsided. This minimizes the potential long-term complications associated with permanent IVC filters, such as filter fracture, migration, and perforation. The OptionELITE filter's retrievability ensures that patients are not subjected to unnecessary long-term risks, thereby improving overall treatment outcomes.

Clinical Performance in the PRESERVE Trial

The **PRESERVE trial** (Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters) is a landmark study designed to evaluate the safety and efficacy of various IVC filters, including the OptionELITE filter. This multicenter, prospective trial included 1,421 patients across

54 sites in the United States, making it one of the most comprehensive studies of its kind.

Safety

Complications: The OptionELITE filter demonstrated a low incidence of major complications in the PRESERVE trial. Significant filter migration, defined as movement greater than 20 mm, was reported in only 2.0% of cases. Importantly, there were no instances of filter fracture, a complication that can lead to serious outcomes such as fragment embolization and perforation of the IVC or adjacent organs. This low rate of migration and absence of fractures underscore the structural integrity and reliable performance of the OptionELITE filter.

Perforation and Thrombosis: The rate of clinically significant perforation, where the filter penetrates the IVC wall, and caval thrombotic occlusion (complete blockage of the IVC by a thrombus) was minimal. These complications are serious concerns with IVC filters, as they can lead to significant morbidity. The design and material properties of the OptionELITE filter, including its flexible nitinol construction and secure anchoring system, contribute to these favorable outcomes by reducing mechanical stress on the vena cava and preventing thrombus formation.

Efficacy

Prevention of PE: The primary efficacy endpoint of the PRESERVE trial was the prevention of PE in high-risk patients. The OptionELITE filter was highly effective in this regard, with a low incidence of PE reported among the study participants. The filter's ability to capture emboli and prevent them from traveling to the pulmonary arteries is critical for its role in preventing PE, which can be life-threatening. The efficacy of the OptionELITE filter in capturing emboli is attributed to its design, which maximizes the surface area available for trapping thrombi while maintaining a flow-through configuration to minimize blood flow obstruction (Argon Medical Devices) (Duomed).

Clinical Outcomes: The PRESERVE trial demonstrated that the OptionELITE filter performed well across a diverse patient population, including various demographics and clinical scenarios. This versatility highlights the filter's effectiveness in a wide range of clinical settings, from patients with acute DVT to those with chronic thromboembolic conditions. The consistent performance of the OptionELITE filter in preventing thromboembolic events across different patient groups underscores its reliability and adaptability (Argon Medical Devices) (Duomed).

Retrievability

High Retrieval Success Rate: The design of the OptionELITE filter facilitates high rates of successful retrieval. In the PRESERVE trial, 96.8% of first-attempt retrievals were successful, demonstrating the filter's ease of removal. Successful retrieval is defined as the complete removal of the filter from the IVC without complications, such as fragment embolization or significant injury to the IVC wall. The high success rate of retrieval is crucial for minimizing long-term complications and ensuring that patients can have the filter removed when it is no longer needed.

Indwell Time: The average indwell time for successfully retrieved filters was approximately 4.3 months. This duration indicates that the filter can remain in place long enough

to provide effective protection during periods of high thromboembolic risk, while still allowing for easy retrieval when the risk has diminished. The ability to maintain efficacy over this period, combined with the high retrieval success rate, enhances the filter's utility in managing venous thromboembolism (VTE).

Positive Clinical Data

The positive performance of the OptionELITE filter in the PRESERVE trial is further supported by additional clinical studies that have evaluated its safety, efficacy, and retrievability.

Albertson et al. (2023): This study, published in the *Journal of Vascular Surgery: Venous and Lymphatic Disorders*, examined 603 OptionELITE filters over six years. The findings indicated low complication rates and a high retrieval success rate of 99%. The average indwell time was 14.8 months, suggesting that the filter can be safely left in place for extended periods if necessary. The study highlighted the filter's robust performance in real-world clinical settings, reinforcing its reliability and safety (Albertson et al., 2023).

Johnson et al. (2023): Another significant study published in the *Journal of Vascular Surgery: Venous and Lymphatic Disorders* reported on the outcomes of the PRESERVE trial at 12 months. This study emphasized the filter's effectiveness in preventing PE and its low incidence of major complications. The data from this study provided further evidence of the filter's strong safety and efficacy profiles, making it a compelling choice for PE prevention in high-risk patients (Johnson et al., 2023).

Additional Study Data

The **IVC Filter Retrievability Study** by Stibbs et al. (2023) offers additional insights into the retrievability of the OptionELITE filter. This retrospective literature review assessed the overall retrieval success rates across multiple studies. The review demonstrated a 97.8% success rate for retrieval of the Option and OptionELITE filters. Notably, 95.5% of retrievals were performed using the standard snare and sheath technique, which is recommended by the Instructions for Use (IFU) for transjugular retrieval. The high success rate and the standardization of retrieval techniques contribute to the overall safety and effectiveness of the filter (5†sources)

Conclusion

The **OptionELITE filter** has consistently demonstrated exceptional performance across both clinical trials and real-world applications, solidifying its reputation as a highly effective and reliable medical device for the prevention of pulmonary embolism (PE). This conclusion is drawn from comprehensive data that highlights the filter's robust safety, efficacy, and ease of retrieval, making it a preferred choice in the management of venous thromboembolism (VTE).

Safety

The OptionELITE filter's design minimizes the risk of complications that are commonly associated with IVC filters. The single-piece nitinol construction may significantly reduce the potential for filter fracture, a critical advantage over multi-piece designs. Clinical studies, including the PRESERVE trial, have reported a notably low incidence of significant filter migration and no occurrences of filter fracture, underscoring the device's structural integrity and

reliability. The filter's design effectively prevents both cranial and caudal migration, further enhancing patient safety by ensuring the filter remains securely in place within the IVC.

Efficacy

In terms of efficacy, the OptionELITE filter excels at capturing emboli, thereby preventing them from reaching the pulmonary arteries and causing PE. The PRESERVE trial and other studies have shown that the filter effectively reduces the incidence of PE in high-risk patients. This is achieved through its large surface area and flow-through design, which maximizes emboli capture while maintaining adequate blood flow through the IVC. The filter's performance across various patient demographics and clinical scenarios highlights its versatility and ability to provide consistent protection against thromboembolic events.

Retrievability

One of the standout features of the OptionELITE filter is its ease of retrievability. The filter's open apex design facilitates straightforward snaring and removal, which is critical for minimizing long-term complications associated with permanent filter implantation. The high retrieval success rate reported in the PRESERVE trial (96.8% on the first attempt) and other studies reflects the filter's design efficiency and the effectiveness of standard retrieval techniques. The ability to retrieve the filter easily ensures that it can be removed once the transient risk of PE has subsided, thus reducing the risk of long-term adverse events.

Clinical Validation

The OptionELITE filter's performance has been validated by extensive clinical research, including landmark studies like the PRESERVE trial and comprehensive reviews like the IVC Filter Retrievability Study by Stibbs et al. These studies have consistently shown that the filter provides a high degree of protection against PE, with low complication rates and high retrieval success. For instance, the study by Albertson et al. reported a 99% retrieval success rate over an average indwell time of 14.8 months, further affirming the filter's reliability and safety in long-term use.

Practical Implications

The practical implications of these findings are significant for clinical practice. The OptionELITE filter offers a robust solution for patients at transient risk of PE, combining ease of deployment, effective emboli capture, and reliable retrieval. Its design and material properties ensure durability and compatibility with the dynamic environment of the IVC. For healthcare providers, the filter's high retrieval success rate and low complication profile translate to improved patient outcomes and reduced long-term risks, making it a cost-effective and clinically sound choice for PE prevention with the ability to be removed as soon as the risk of pulmonary embolism is mitigated.

Broader Impact

The positive clinical outcomes associated with the OptionELITE filter, and the PRESERVE study as a whole, not only support IVC filter use when clinically indicated, but also contribute to broader clinical guidelines and standards for IVC filter utilization. The PRESERVE performance data can inform best practices and help shape recommendations for the management of VTE, particularly

in patients with transient risk factors for PE. Offering a reliable and safe option for PE prevention, the OptionELITE filter helps address a critical need in the management of thromboembolic diseases, ultimately improving patient care and safety for populations at risk for symptomatic embolic events.

Final Thoughts

In conclusion, the OptionELITE filter stands out as a sound option for preventing pulmonary embolism in high-risk patients. Its advanced design features, superior safety profile, proven efficacy, and ease of retrieval collectively make it an invaluable tool in the management of venous thromboembolism and PE prevention. The consistent positive outcomes from various clinical studies such as the PRESERVE trial and real-world applications underscore its role as an adjunct to safe and effective intervention, providing peace of mind for both patients and healthcare providers. As the medical community continues to prioritize patient safety and outcomes, the PRESERVE study validates the use of IVC filters when clinical indication validates their inclusion in an overall plan for venous thrombosis management that is consistent with societal guidelines and accepted treatment practices.

References

- ACC Maintenance. (2016, October 31). <https://www.acc.org/latest-in-cardiology/articles/2016/10/31/09/28/appropriate-use-of-inferior-vena-cava-filters>
- Bikdeli, B., & Bikdeli, B. (2016, October 10). Updates on Advanced Therapies for Acute Pulmonary Embolism. <https://doi.org/10.21859/ijcp-010301>
- Bikdeli, B., Chatterjee, S., Desai, N R., Kirtane, A J., Desai, M., & Bracken, M B. (2018, January 1). Inferior Vena Cava Filters to Prevent Pulmonary Embolism: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvsv.2017.10.008>
- Gillespie, D L., Spies, J B., Siami, F S., Rectenwald, J E., White, R A., & Johnson, M S. (2020, March 5). Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters Study: Design of a unique safety and effectiveness study of inferior vena cava filters in clinical practice.. <https://jvsveno.us.com/retrieve/pii/S2213333X19304366>
- Grewal, S., Chamrthy, M R., & Kalva, S P. (2016, December 1). Complications of inferior vena cava filters. <https://doi.org/10.21037/cdt.2016.09.08>
- Kaufman, J A., Barnes, G D., Chaer, R A., Cuschieri, J., Eberhardt, R T., Johnson, M., Kuo, W T., Murin, S., Patel, S., Rajasekhar, A., Weinberg, I., & Gillespie, D L. (2020, October 1). Society of Interventional Radiology Clinical Practice Guideline for Inferior Vena Cava Filters in the Treatment of Patients with Venous Thromboembolic Disease. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvir.2020.06.014>
- Kelkar, A H., & Rajasekhar, A. (2020, December 4). Inferior vena cava filters: a framework for evidence-based use. <https://doi.org/10.1182/hematology.2020000149>
- Sobieszczyk, P. (2018, April 15). Factors to Consider Regarding the Need for Inferior Vena Cava Filters.. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S033062018300720>

Johnson, M. S., Spies, J. B., Scott, K. T., Kato, B. S., Mu, X., Rectenwald, J. E., ... & Zuckerman, D. A. (2023). Predicting the Safety and Effectiveness of Inferior Vena Cava Filters (PRESERVE): Outcomes at 12 months. *Journal of Vascular Surgery: Venous and Lymphatic Disorders*, 11(3), 573-585.e6.

Albertson, N., Rice, M., Schmitz, A., Eskew, J., Haste, P., & Johnson, M. S. (2023). Clinical and imaging outcomes of OptionELITE vena cava filter placement procedures. *Journal of Vascular Surgery: Venous and Lymphatic Disorders*, 11(2), 310-317. doi: 10.1016/j.jvsv.2022.08.005

Stibbs, et al, Inferior Vena Cava Filter Retrievability: OptionElite™Retrivabilty Data in a Retrospective Literature Review. *ScienceOpen Posters*. 2022. DOI: 10.14293/S2199-1006.1.SOR-.PPIMMFN.v1

Metric	Value
Total Patients	1421
Patients with DVT/PE at Placement	1019
Major Complications - Migration	3
Major Complications - Embolization	4
Major Complications - Perforation	15.4% (211 patients)
Post-Placement DVT	74
Post-Placement PE	23
Caval Thrombotic Occlusion	15
Retrievable Filters Removed (%)	49.3% of retrievable filters
All Filters Removed (%)	44.5% of all filters
Retrieval Procedure-Related Adverse Events (%)	1.8% (1 death)
Successful Retrievals (First Attempt) (%)	96.8%
Mean Retrieval Time (days)	101.5
Median Retrieval Time (days)	86.3

Figure 1. PRESERVE DATA TABLE

Figure 2. OptionELITE IVC Filter